

How do Constitutions Remember?

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, many societies around the globe are struggling with numerous difficult problems in terms of memorializing the past. Memorialization processes are crucial to the construction of collective memory and national identity. The term collective memory refers to shared images or representations of the past (Halbwachs 1925) and is traditionally cited as an essential component of nation-building projects. Nations are “politically imagined communities” (Anderson 1991), meaning that their origin is artificial, and collective memory creates an emotional space within which people can imagine themselves as belonging to the same nation. Whether immaterial and takes the form of symbols and historical narratives, or material in the form of museums, monuments, and memorials, memory has a strong integrative force. It binds the nation together by providing for a group’s unity, cohesion, and solidarity (Calhoun 1993, 211). Conversely, memory excludes. In telling narratives about the nation’s past, it draws the boundaries between the common We-identity and the otherness, thus allowing differentiation among nations and nation-states.

The Constitution forms an important part of the memorialization process, but its role in forging and promoting the collective memory of the nation has been largely neglected. Although to a varying degree, almost all existing Constitutions contain some references to the past that create and define the nation. For example, the constitutional term *We the People* is the symbolic representation of unity which might not exist in reality (Probst 2015, 2) but is imagined and bound together through the Constitution by relying on components of collective memory: national symbols, such as the flag, anthem, oaths, and mottos, and very often historical narratives about travails and triumphs on the journey to nationhood. Provisions containing collective memory can be generally found in Preambles, opening declarations, but also normative parts of Constitutions. They may be further enclosed in separate pre-constitutional or extra-constitutional documents, such as declarations of independence.

By incorporating collective memory, Constitutions attempt to answer the most fundamental questions: *Who are we?*, *What binds us together?*, and *Whose is the state?*. The answers to these questions are not aesthetical but may have deep consequences on the constitutional order. Collective memory may help the construction of more inclusive societies and can even serve peace projects and reconciliatory politics after violent conflicts. Very often, however, memory represents an obstacle to achieving these goals. Manipulations of memory for political ends may lead to symbolic conflicts which can easily turn into tensions and wars within and between states (Wagoner, Brescó 2016, 3).

This draft paper focuses on the complex relationship between collective memory and national identity through the lens of the Constitution. It first reconstructs the existing theoretical framework that links memory to the Constitution and then explores, from a comparative perspective, the different modes Constitutions employ for dealing with the past. The main aim is to show that not necessarily Constitutions, by incorporating collective memory, are used as instruments to promote the integration

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or reconciliation of societies, but that they can be also used as tools for creating regimes of exclusions, justifying illiberal turns, and even legitimizing armed conflicts. To explain the latter dynamics, the paper introduces the notion of emotional constitutionalism, with the aim to propose a new theory of constitutional interpretation.

2. The role of the Constitution in forging collective memory

In its seminal work on the *lieux de mémoire*, the French historian Pierre Nora (1984, 16) claims that every Constitution is a place of memory, that is a place in which present days nations deposit their memories of past glorious and dramatic events. Although the role of the Constitution in memorialization processes has rarely been explored, some further indications may be found in the literature. For example, Johannes Snyman (1998, 312) believes that memory occupies a central position in constitutional interpretation. For him, the constitution-making is a strategy of a politics of memory, while the Constitution continues the institutionalization of memory within the public realm. Snyman compares the Constitution with other places of memory, namely monuments and memorials. Monuments demarcate a decisive moment such as the triumph or victory in a war as a (new) beginning and celebrate heroic figures. Memorials, on the contrary, demarcate a decisive moment as an ending, reminding us that what is remembered may never happen again, and commemorate the victims. For Snyman, the Constitution as a strategy of politics of memory should be ideally used to prevent the recurrence of social evil.

Lourens du Plessis (2000, 385) further argues that a Constitution is both the author and narrator of the nation's past. In his words, the potency with which the Constitution can mould a politics of memory equals the authority with which it can shape the politics of the day. Following Snyman, du Plessis introduces the notions of monumental constitutionalism and memorial constitutionalism and describes the Constitution as a monument and memorial at the same time. As monuments, Constitutions celebrate; as memorials, they commemorate. Finally, Karin van Marle (2007, 215) compares the Constitution to the archive, defining the latter as a place where things commence, the place from which order is given, and the place that contains memory. As the archive traces only particular aspects of the past, the Constitution similarly traces only particular aspects and interpretations of the past and nation. Furthermore, as the archive simultaneously urges to remember and forget, the Constitution does the same, with the risk to destroy all traces without any reminder of what is other to the past of the country it engraves.

These writings are important because they all sustain that what is contained in Constitutions is collective memory rather than the history of the nation. The two terms, memory and history, are not synonyms. As Fogu and Kansteiner (2006, 284) observe memory has always enjoyed a very complicated relationship with the truth. It is not history but is sometimes made of similar material. While history has facts and truth as goals, memory creates myths about a nation's past. It thus pertains to the world of illusion and for this reason it is often associated with the fabrication of history, invented traditions, and historical revisionism (Hobsbawm and Ranger 1983; Nora 1989, 7). Memory is further inherently selective, meaning that it implies both remembering and forgetting. By choosing particular interpretations of the nation's past, Constitutions make deep political choices. They may close the ranks of the common We-identity and decide who is included in and who is excluded from the concept of the nation, as well as what is acceptable and legitimate to think of as official national history. As the next sections will try to show, it is on the basis of these choices that Constitutions may express an integratory and/or reconciliatory potentials, but also legitimize regimes of exclusions, tensions, and wars.

3. The integrative potential of constitutional memory

Dieter Grimm (2005, 193) calls the integrative potential of the Constitution its ability to develop a collective identity and indicates that this presupposes a Constitution marked by a high degree of

inclusivity. The extent of the inclusiveness depends very often on how Constitutions deal with the past. For instance, both the US and German Constitutions are generally considered successful cases of the integrative potential of Constitutions (Grimm 2005, 202; Orgad 2010, 731). In both cases, however, Constitution and collective memory are deeply intertwined.

In the US, the three founding documents – the 1776 Declaration of Independence, the 1789 Federal Constitution, and the 1791 Bill Of Rights – form an important part of national collective memory (Paul 2014, 200). For example, the day of the adoption of the Declaration of Independence is a national holiday that celebrates the founding of the nation. The Federal Constitution opens with the famous phrase *We the People* without setting the boundaries of a political community. This has allowed the country to expand over time its definition of who belongs. The Fifteenth Amendment (1870), for instance, prohibited the federal government and each state from denying or abridging a citizen's right to vote on account of race, color, or previous condition of servitude, while the Nineteenth Amendment (1920) granted women the right to vote. This development was possible as the Federal Constitution sustains a very particular narrative about the national identity in which the country is understood to be the quintessential civic polity (Rana 2015, 266). In this narrative, the Federal Constitution, which gives concrete substance to the civic ideals, represents the proof that the Americans have produced a unique phenomenon in history, a single unified and powerful nation committed to inclusive liberal values. The narrative about the American civic identity has played a powerful role in creating a more inclusive national community, but it has also made it more difficult to address the colonial past and slavery as it considers the country free and equal since its origins. It thus neglects to depict, for example, that the constitutional founding did not end the colonization but empowered a new phase of expropriation (*ibidem*) or that the Federal Constitution did not abolish slavery as this occurred after the American Civil War (1861- 65) (Paul 2014, 167).

In Germany, the 1949 Basic Law was adopted after the country's defeat in WWII with the primary intent to prevent the recurrence of inhumane practices of the Nazi era (Ackerman 1997, 778). To this end, the Constitution introduced the notion of militant democracy and the promise of “never again.” Although the Basic Law does not expressly mention the Nazi past, its Preamble opens by recognizing the responsibility of German people before God and man, as well as their determination to promote world peace as an equal partner in a united Europe, while Article 1 is devoted to human dignity. The definition of national identity by relying on traditional identity markers, such as the common past was out of the question as the past was closely associated to the Holocaust (Grimm, 2005, 198). This led to the development of the notion of constitutional patriotism, that is the idea that political attachment ought to center on the norms, values, and procedures of a liberal democratic Constitution (Müller and Scheppele 2008, 67).

4. Constitutional memory and reconciliatory politics

Andrew Schaap (2007, 9) argues that the Constitution is of crucial importance for moving away from a divisive past towards a common future. For him, the reconciliation should be initiated by the invocation of the “We” as the basis of a new political order. In this sense, the act of the Constitution requires conceiving the present as a point of origin, as well as that former enemies promise never again in order to condition the possibility of community in the future. Constitutions can consequently act as stabilizing forces for the future and bring different groups to live together. From a practical perspective, of course, the realization of such a Constitution is not an easy task but post-apartheid South Africa probably represents the most famous attempt to achieve this goal.

The constitutional transition of South Africa started with the 1993 interim Constitution, which aim was to give birth to the people and verbalized the quest for reconciliation that would overcome the atrocities of the past (Botha 1998, 344). It contained a Postable (or Postscript) entitled “National Unity and Reconciliation and decreed” which provided a “historic bridge between the past of a deeply divided society characterized by strife, conflict, untold suffering and injustice, and a future founded on the recognition of human rights, democracy, and peaceful co-existence and development

opportunities for all South Africans, irrespective of colour, race, class, belief or sex.” The Postamble further established that the pursuit of national unity, the well-being of all South-African citizens, and peace require reconciliation between the people of South Africa and the reconstruction of society. The term transitional constitutionalism was consequently introduced to depict the Constitution as a bridge from the old to the new South Africa (du Plessis 2015, 1345).

Much of the Postamble has survived in the Preamble of the (final) 1996 Constitution which marked the second phase of the country’s transition. It recognizes the injustices of the past and honours those who suffered for justice and freedom. The reasons for the adoption of the Constitution are identified in the need for healing the divisions of the past and building a unified and democratic South Africa able to take its rightful place as a sovereign state in the family of nations. Section 1 of the Constitution tells also what the new state should be like by proclaiming the values of constitutional democracy, including human dignity, equality, and freedom to be at the core of South African constitutionalism (*ibidem*). Lidija R. Basta Fleiner (2003, 312) noted that the South African case shows a specific inclusive nature of the constitution-making process that gave people the feeling of “ownership” of the Constitution.

5. Ethnicization of constitutional memory as means of divisions and wars

Not always, however, constitutional frameworks are so generous as to allow an inclusive polity. Scholars have pointed out the issue of “ethnicization of memory” to describe a situation in which interpretations of the past are ethnically exclusive, creating different symbolic meanings of common events in people who belong to different ethnic groups (Corkalo et al. 2004, 157). The mixture between universal democratic values and the persistence of ethnic traditions is present, for instance, in many Constitutions of Central, Eastern, and Southeastern Europe. What is problematic in these cases, especially in multicultural societies, is that Constitutions embody only the narrative of the dominant ethnic group without leaving space for narratives of minority groups that may have also suffered in an undemocratic past. The constitutionalization of ethno-centric narratives may further lead to declaring the supremacy of the dominant ethnic nation over other ethnic minorities. The latter development can be observed, in particular, in several countries that emerged from the dissolution of the former Yugoslavia.

For example, the 1991 Constitution of Slovenia opens with a Preamble that celebrates the nation’s struggle for independence and self-determination by establishing that Slovenes have established their national identity and asserted their statehood in a century-long struggle for national liberation which gave the basis, among others, for the adoption of the current Constitution. Robert M. Hayden (1992, 659) observes that the Preamble refers only to the dominant Slovene nation, without even mentioning other minority communities such as Italians and Hungarians. Article 3 of the Constitution further explains that Slovenia is a state of all of its citizens, but also that it is founded on the permanent and inalienable right of the Slovene nation to self-determination. Jelka Zorn (2008, 58) sees in such proclamations ethnocentric tendencies, while Ciril Ribicic (1992, 65) describes the recurrence of the term Slovene nation as a disfiguration of the constitutional foundation of statehood. In his view, this repeated formulation places minority ethnic communities and citizens who are not Slovenes in a different position, thus qualifying the country as an ethno-democratic order.

References to ethno-centric narratives may be further found in the 1990 Constitution of Croatia which opens with a Preamble entitled “Historical foundations.” The latter pays homage to the Croat millennial national identity and the continuity of statehood by tracing the origins of the state and the nation in the creation of Croatian principalities in the 7th Century, the medieval kingdom of the 9th Century, and a series of other state formations which finally led to the establishment of today’s Croatia. On this basis, the original version of the Preamble made it clear that Croatia has been established primarily as a state of the Croat nation and secondarily as a state of other nations and national minorities. The initial text of the Preamble listed some but not all minority groups living in the country. Mila Dragojevic (2019, 10) observes that such a constitutional framework contributed to

the rise of political tensions before the explosion of violence and the war of the 1990s as it downgraded the status of Serbs from previous constitutive people to that of other nations and national minorities. Moreover, the normative part of the Constitution introduced the official national symbols, such as the ethnically Croat coat of arms that Serbs further associated with the Independent State of Croatia – the country's WWII pro-Nazi regime, responsible for sending thousands of Jews, Serbs, Roma and anti-fascist Croats to concentration camps.

In 2010, a constitutional reform introduced some novelties. On the one hand, it added to the Preamble a list of 22 national minorities living in the country without erasing, however, the prevalence of Croatian nation over other ethnic groups. On the other hand, it also introduced a very specific narrative about the Homeland War (the official name of the conflict that took place in Croatia from 1991-95 during the violent break-up of Yugoslavia) by defining it as a defensive, just, and legitimate war. This definition resembles the official narrative of the war of the 1990s, which emphasizes its defensive character and considers it as the resistance of the Croatian nation to the greater Serbian aggression. The narrative, however, does not clarify that Croatia considered during the Wars of the 1990s part of Bosnia-Herzegovina as its own territory and that the country's intervention in Bosnia-Herzegovina, formally justified as a support to the Croat community, led to the creation of a new autonomous region, Herceg-Bosna, with the intention of annexation. In addition, this narrative does not take into account the civilian victims of the war, as well as the exodus of approximately 300,000 Serbs following military actions for which Croatia was accused of ethnic cleansing of Serb population. The narrative about the Homeland War is thus extremely divisive: for the dominant Croatian nation it represents a powerful narrative positioned at the very heart of national identity; for national minorities, especially the Serb community, it represents a synonym for ethnic cleansing.

Similar trends can be found in the original text of the Preamble of the 1991 Constitution of North Macedonia. The latter was adopted by "Taking as the points of departure the historical, cultural, spiritual and statehood heritage of the Macedonian people and their struggle over centuries for national and social freedom as well as for the creation of their own state." On this basis, the Preamble declared that Macedonia was established as a nation-state of the Macedonian people as well as other nationalities that reside therein. These constitutional statements led the Albanian faction to employ violence in order to force a constitutional amendment that would transform the country into a binational state (Orgad 2010, 717). Following the 2001 Ohrid Agreement, the Preamble was amended by defining as citizens of the Republic of Macedonia the Macedonian people, as well as citizens living within its borders who are part of the Albanian people, the Turkish people, the Vlach people, the Serbian people, the Romany people, and the Bosniak people. The definition of Macedonia as a nation-state of the Macedonian people was also erased but this caused resentment among Macedonians who felt this change was forced upon them by violence and international pressure (*ibidem*). Ethnic Albanians, on the contrary, claim that the Preamble still implies their inferior status because of their linkage to other minorities. The superiority of the Macedonian nation has been symbolically preserved in the Preamble as Macedonian people is the only adjective derived from a nationality written with a capital letter – a grammatically incorrect form in the Macedonian language – whereas the rest of the nationalities are written with the correct lower-case letter (Shasivari 2011, 31).

Another example is Serbia, where the 2006 Constitution opens by asserting "the state tradition of the Serb people" and the equality of all citizens and ethnic communities. Article 1 further defines Serbia as a state of Serbian people and all citizens who live in it. Although the Preamble does not expressly contain invocations of centuries-long traditions, it defines Kosovo and Metohija as an "integral part of Serbia." The Constitution was adopted before Kosovo declared its independence in 2008 and the main reason for its adoption was to constitutionally safeguard the territorial integrity of the state by defining Kosovo as an autonomous province in Serbia. The importance of Kosovo for Serbia derives, however, from the link to the medieval past. Not only is Kosovo perceived as the center of medieval Serbia, but the Kosovo myth is positioned at the center of national identity. The latter describes the medieval Battle of Kosovo which led to the military defeat of Serbian forces by

the Ottoman armies in 1389. This defeat is described by the myth as a choice of heavenly glory over earthly power. The explicit or implicit constitutionalization of the link between present-day states and medieval state formations seems problematic. Not only do historians agree that this link does not exist (Fine 2009, 15), but its proclamation may legitimize acts of aggression. For example, in the Yugoslav wars of the 1990s, Croatia and Serbia tried to recreate the borders of medieval kingdoms by using Bosnia-Herzegovina as a theater of the conflict. Before the ethnic cleansing, Serbia even evoked the Kosovo battle with the fear that the Ottomans would return and reclaim Serbia and rape its women; this fear was transferred to modern Muslim Bosniacs, who were labeled as Turks (Bar-Tal 2013, 148).

6. Concluding remarks

The short description of different modes Constitutions may use for dealing with the past shows that not necessarily present-day states are defined through concepts such as civic nationalism, or constitutional theories, such as constitutional patriotism, capable of fighting against emotional politics, but that states may also define themselves by positioning founding myths and symbols at the basis of their Constitutions. This resembles a practice I call emotional constitutionalism. It assumes that the constitutionalization of founding myths and symbols produces a surplus of meaning within the Constitution and that this should become an object of constitutional interpretation. As the case of the Yugoslav successor states shows, rigid, ethno-centric narratives about the past can be used by Constitutions to justify the creation of regimes of exclusions and the consequent existence of nation-states defined primarily in terms of ethnicity, as well as to legitimize constitutional memory to operate as official national history. In these cases, the elevation of collective memory to the constitutional level not only precludes the integration or reconciliation of societies but may further create the constitutional basis for legitimizing divisions and tensions alongside ethnic lines that can easily turn into armed conflicts.

The Yugoslav wars of the 1990s are not the only example of this kind. Political analysts have stressed that between 1989 and 1996, for instance, 95 of 101 armed conflicts identified in the world were intra-states and identity-driven conflicts and the vast majority of them were conflicts about the correct interpretation of history (Harris and Reilly 1998, 15). This type of war is notably more intense, brutal, cruel, and emotionally charged with civilians as the main targets. In all of these cases, Constitutions were not capable to contain the conflict. On the contrary, the more recent Russia's invasion of Ukraine shows that the constitutionalization of collective memory may legitimize also conflicts between states (Pistan 2022, 1). Constitutional law should take notice of such developments as peace and war may also depend on how Constitutions deal with the past.

References

- Ackerman B (1997). "The Rise of World Constitutionalism", *Virginia Law Review*, 4, 771-797.
- Andrew Schaap (2007). "The Time of Reconciliation and the Space for Politics", in Veitch S. (ed.), *Law and the Politics of Reconciliation*, London-New York: Routledge, 9-32.
- Bar-Tal D (2013). *Intractable Conflicts Socio-Psychological Foundations and Dynamics*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Basta Fleiner L.R (2003). "Constitution Making and nation Building," in R.J. Blindenbacher, R. Blindenbacher, A. Koller, *Federalism in a Changing World: Learning from Each Other*. Montreal, McGill-Queen's Press, 308-324.
- Benedict A (1991). *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London and New York: Verso.
- Botha H (1998). "Constitutionalism and the Politics of Memory: A Response to Professors Rubinfeld and Snyman," *Acta Juridica*, 342-348.

- Calhoun C (1993). "Nationalism and Ethnicity". *Annual Review of Sociology*, 19, 211-239.
- Corkalo D, Ajdukovic D, Weinstein H, Stover E, Djipa D, & Biro M. (2004). "Neighbors again? Inter-Community Relations after Ethnic Violence," in E. Stover & H. Weinstein (eds.) *My neighbor, my enemy: Justice and community in the aftermath of mass atrocity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 143- 161.
- Dragojevic M (2019). *Amoral Communities: Collective Crimes in Times of War*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Du Plessis L (2000). "The South African Constitution as Memory and Promise". *Stellenbosch Law Review*, 11, 385-394.
- Du Plessis L (2015). "Theoretical (dis-) position and strategic leitmotifs in constitutional interpretation in South Africa", *PER / PELJ*, 5, 1332-1365.
- Fine J.V.A (2006). *When Ethnicity Did Not Matter in the Balkans. A Study of Identity in Pre-Nationalist Croatia, Dalmatia and Slavonia in the Medieval and Early Modern Periods*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Fogu C, Kansteiner W (2006). "The Politics of Memory and the Poetics of History", in R. Ned Lebow , W. Kansteiner, C. Fogu (eds), *The Politics of Memory in Postwar Europe*, Durham-NC-London: Duke University Press, 284-306.
- Grimm D (2005). "Integration by Constitution". *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 3, 193-220.
- Halbwachs M (1980). *The Collective Memory*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Harris P, Reilly B (1998). *Democracy and Deep-rooted Conflict: Options for Negotiators*, International IDEA, Stockholm.
- Hayden, R.M (1992). "Constitutional Nationalism in the Formerly Yugoslav Republics." *Slavic Review*, 51, 654-673.
- Heike P (2014). *The Myths That Made America An Introduction to American Studies*. Bielefeld: Transcript Verlag.
- Hobsbawm E, Ranger T (eds.) (1983). *The Invention of Tradition*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Müller J-W, Scheppele K.L (2008). "Constitutional patriotism: An introduction". *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 1, 67-71.
- Nora P (1989). "Between Memory and History: Les Lieux de Mémoire". *Representations*, 26, 7-24.
- Nora P (ed.) (1984-1992). *Les lieux de mémoire*, 3 tomes. Paris: Gallimard.
- Orgad L (2010). "The preamble in constitutional interpretation". *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 4, 714-738
- Pistan C (2022). "Alarming Alterations: How Memory Politics Turned the Russian Constitution into a War Weapon." PONARS Eurasia Policy Memo No. 798.
- Probst L (2015). "Founding Myths in European Constitution-Building." Available at http://www.monnet-centre.uni-bremen.de/pdf/VerfProz/5_Probst.pdf.
- Rana A (2015). "Colonialism and Constitutional Memory". *UC Irvine Law Review*, 2, 263-288.
- Ribicic C (1992). "Predlog za amandmajsko spremembo tretjega člana nove ustave." *Teorija in praksa*, 29, 65-69.
- Shasivari J (2011). "Constitutional development in the Republic of Macedonia and ethnic (in)equality." *20 Years of the Constitution of the Republic of Macedonia*, 9(35), 31-40.
- Shasivari J (2011). "Constitutional developments in the Republic of Macedonia and ethnic. (in)equality." *Political Thought*, 35(9), 31-41.
- Snyman J (1998). "Interpretation and the Politics of Memory," *Acta Juridica*, 312-337.

- Van Marle Karin (2007). “Constitution as Archive”, in Veitch S (ed.), *Law and the Politics of Reconciliation*. London-New York: Routledge, 215-228.
- Wagoner B, Ignacio B (2016). “Conflict and Memory: The Past in the Present Peace and Conflict”. *Journal of Peace Psychology*, 22, 3-4.
- Zorn J (2007). ““We, the Ethno-citizens of Ethno-democracy” - The Formation of Slovene Citizenship.” *Journal for the Critique of Science*, 52-70.